

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF MODERN MONETARY POLICY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In this article, the primary problems and reforms of the financial sector are studied in detail, and the importance and updates of modern financial policy in our country are described.

Keywords: financial policy, social life, banking activity, inflation, modern problems, etc.

Now, inflation is one of several issues central banks are concerned about. Rapidly changing economic conditions leave less policy space, while structural forces—geopolitical fragmentation, climate change, an aging workforce, and the emergence of digital money—are making the fundamental task of monetary policy much more complex. The mandates of central banks and even their independence are coming under increasing political pressure. These new forces and other factors raise questions about what changes in the nature of monetary policy may be needed in the future. In this issue, prominent authors present their thoughts on how central bankers can navigate an increasingly complex world.

Monetary theory in economics is represented by various directions of scientific thought, and not by a single unified model. Each of these areas highlights different factors that determine inflation dynamics and recommends different policy responses. Different challenges arose at different times, and each of them required its own approach in terms of economic policy. Now, due to a

new wave of inflation, it is necessary to once again change the emphasis in monetary policy. The prevailing conceptual framework that central banks have followed since the global financial crisis that began in 2008 does not pay particular attention to the most pressing challenges ahead and fails to mitigate their potentially dire consequences in this new environment. After a long period of low interest rates and low inflation, the world economy is entering a phase characterized by high inflation and high levels of both public and private debt. Fifteen years ago, central banks saw an urgent need to incorporate concerns about financial stability and deflation into their traditional economic models and developed unconventional tools to address both issues.

While financial stability remains a concern, there are important differences between current conditions and those that have emerged since the global financial crisis.

- Government debt is currently at a high level, so any increase in interest rates to ward off inflationary threats increases the cost of servicing the debt, with immediate and significant adverse fiscal consequences for the government. It has also been clear since the onset of the COVID-19 crisis in early 2020 that fiscal policy can be a significant driver of inflation.

- Instead of deflationary pressures, most countries experience excessive inflation. This means that there is now a clear choice between monetary policy, which attempts to reduce aggregate demand by raising interest rates, and policy that seeks to promote financial stability.

- The nature and frequency of shocks have changed. In past periods, shocks were mainly caused by increases or decreases in demand, with the exception of supply shocks during the so-called stagflation of the 1970s.

There are a lot of shocks now: in terms of demand or supply, associated with idiosyncratic or systemic risks, of a transitional or permanent nature. It is difficult to determine the true nature of these shocks in time to respond. Central bankers

need to be less picky. Monetary policy requires a modified approach that is resilient to sudden and unexpected changes in the macroeconomic scenario. Measures that are effective in one macroeconomic environment may have unintended consequences when conditions suddenly change. This article will look at what major challenges central banks will face, what monetary theories will take center stage, and how central banks can avoid overconfidence and the tactics of old battles. Most importantly, the central bank must keep public opinion on its side, because the public is the main source of its strength and independence. This means that the central bank must effectively communicate the rationale for its actions to maintain public support, especially in the face of inflation caused by fiscal policy measures. The central bank ultimately maintains its dominance if it can credibly promise that it will not bail out the government by monetizing government debt in the event of default.

To address these challenges, central banks should return to a monetary policy stance in which stabilizing inflation expectations is a central priority. Policy cannot be tightened only after inflation has risen. Instead, central banks should take action as soon as the warning lights come on. Central banks must take into account both household and financial market expectations of future inflation, as these expectations shape both aggregate demand conditions and asset prices.

At the same time, the successful implementation of reforms regarding the liberalization of the foreign exchange market is closely related to the improvement of the monetary policy, the strengthening of the activities of commercial banks, and the effectiveness of measures to develop the banking system. It should be noted that the correct acceptance and support of the changes in the monetary and credit sphere by the population and business entities is of great importance in the new events that are formed during the revision of the approaches to the implementation of the economic policy. It is known to everyone that the experience of the central banks of developed and developing countries

and the results of the research of independent financial institutions show the undoubted priority of the goal of ensuring price stability in the implementation of monetary policy. The procedure and sequence of monetary policy implementation differs in different countries depending on the characteristics and structural structure of the economy. According to the current Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the main goal of the Central Bank is to ensure the stability of the national currency. In this case, the concept of "national currency stability" can be interpreted in two ways, that is, the stability of the exchange rate against foreign currencies or the stability of its domestic purchasing power. The goals and main directions of the monetary and credit policy of the Central Bank, as well as the clear determination of the obligations to achieve the target indicators of inflation serve to form positive economic expectations in the society. Taking into account that the inflationary expectations of the population are largely related to the dynamics of the exchange rate in the currency market, ensuring the stability of the national currency rate in the short term is one of the important tasks of the monetary policy.

In the development of the main directions of the monetary policy for the period of 2022 and 2023-2024, first of all, it was derived from the goals of ensuring price and financial stability in the economy, reducing the inflation rate to 5% by the end of 2023. The main directions of the monetary and credit policy include the medium-term macroeconomic development forecasts of the Central Bank and the work to be carried out in the monetary and credit sector in the coming years, the measures to be taken by the Central Bank in the event of changes in external and internal economic conditions, and the implementation of the monetary policy. approaches are reflected. The world economy in 2020 due to the introduction of strict quarantine restrictions in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and the global economic crisis caused by it, a decrease in economic activity and disruptions in the supply chain and monetary and fiscal budget

experienced a significant relaxation of its policies.

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